

Huron

also known as "Wendat"

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Native American (North American) Religions, Religious Group

This entry is based upon ethnographic materials that reconstruct the Huron society prior to cultural changes as a result of outside influence. Reconstruction is made possible from accounts written by European traders and Jesuit missionaries during early contacts with the Huron. This entry focuses on the Bear (Attignawantan) and Cord (Attigneenongnahac) subtribes around the time of 1634, which were located between Lake Simcoe and the Georgian Bay in what is now Ontario, Canada. These two subtribes are the largest and oldest of the four Huron subtribes (the other two being the Tahontaenrat and Arendahronon). At the focal time of 1634, the village was the primary unit of daily life, encompassing social, economic, and religious importance. The village was led by a council of elders, a war chief, and a general chief. However, this varied by village and sometimes several chiefs were present. Leaders acted as a council, with no chief outranking others, and holding their position on the basis of ability, experience, success, courage, etc. Religion did not have its own distinct sphere in Huron society, rather, it was a part of all Huron beliefs and practices; "to them, their religion and way of life were one and the same" (Trigger, 1976:75). Consequently, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society. The Huron did not have religious specialists (e.g. a shaman or priest position), rather, chiefs often held ritual offices and duties in addition to their secular roles. The religion did not have a well-defined pantheon of supernatural beings, but the most important deity is the sky, serving as a present but otiose high god. Also present are previously human spirits, but these beings are not discussed in extensive ethnographic details. Non-human supernatural beings include Iouskeha and Aataentsic (two of the most important, best-personified, and most described beings), as well as "...animate spirits [that] resided in the earth, the rivers, lakes, certain rocks, and the sky and had control over journeying, trading, war feasts, disease, and other matters" (Tooker, 1964:80). Religious observances (e.g. taboos, superstitions) were associated with almost all aspects of Huron life, such as subsistence strategies and life cycle events. Four types of feasts were held, including singing (celebratory) feasts, thanksgiving feasts, curing feasts, and farewell feasts.

Date Range: 1615 CE - 1640 CE

Region: Huronia

Region tags: North America, Canada

The Bear (Attignawantan) and Cord (Attigneenongnahac) Huron subtribes living in Huronia around the time of 1634. "...the Huron villages were concentrated in an area that measured no more than 35 miles east to west and 20 miles north to south...on the east the Huron settlements were bounded by Lake Simcoe, on the west by Nottawasaga Bay, the southernmost extension of Georgian Bay. The Huron country was separated from the region to the north by Matchedash Bay, a

narrow inlet also opening onto Georgian bay"
(Trigger, 1969:9).

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Murdock, G.P. (1967). *Ethnographic Atlas*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Source 2: Divale, W. (2004). *Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample*. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 3: Trigger, B. G. (1969). *The Huron*. G. Spindler & L. Spindler (Eds.). NY: Holt, Rinehart, & Winston.
- Source 1: Tooker, E. (1964). An ethnography of the Huron Indians, 1615-1649. *Bulletin of the Bureau of American Ethnology*, 190:1-183.
- Source 2: Trigger, B.G. (1976). *The Children of Aataentsic: A history of the Huron People to 1660*. 2 vols. Montreal.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "The most extensive data on the Huron [from the early 17th century] is that contained in the Jesuit Relations. Each year the Jesuit missionaries working in New France sent back to their Superior in France a report, or relation, of their activities, and each year these reports were edited and printed in France with the intent of gaining support for the missions" (Tooker, 1964:4).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating), coded the Huron's frequency of internal warfare as 1.75, which is between "internal warfare seems to be absent or rare (original code= 1)", and "internal warfare seems to occur once every 3 to 10 years (original code= 2)". Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating), coded the Huron's frequency of external warfare as 4.5, which is between "external warfare seems to occur every year, but usually only during a particular season (original code= 4)", and "external warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year (original code= 5)". Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because the Huron religion was coterminous with the society at large, there is not a system for assigning religious affiliation (see questions below, and Trigger, 1976:75, for more details).

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Because the Huron religion was coterminous with the society at large, there was no form of recruitment of new members (see questions below, and Trigger, 1976:75, for more details).

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: "Like the other people of the Northeast, the Huron lacked specialists who performed regular religious ceremonies on behalf of the whole community, and they did not construct special buildings, shrines, or alters for religious purposes. Religion did not have a well-defined sphere of its own in Huron life, but tended to pervade all of their activities" (Trigger, 1969:91). "...instead of having its own institutionally delimited sphere...religion was indissolubly a part of all the things the Huron believed and did. The Huron did not perceive religion as being a well-defined set of beliefs that an individual could either accept, or substitute with another, at will. To them, their religion and way of life were one and the same. Many of the most important aspects of Huron religion were embraced by the term *onderha*, which meant the "prop" or "foundation" of a country. This term was used to denote the dances, customs, and ceremonies that bound a people together and promoted friendship, solidarity, and goodwill amongst them" (Trigger, 1976:75).

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: No priests are present

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: Religious infrastructure is not present (see Trigger, 1969:91).

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: "The Huron had numerous formal structures that cut across clan and village lines. One such kind of institution was the curing societies, each of which performed specific rituals that were believed to cure certain kinds of disease...Each of the curing societies had a leader, whose office appears to have been hereditary. Very often, these leaders seem to have been important chiefs whose ritual office complemented and strengthened their secular authority" (Trigger, 1969:97-98). "...many of the men who played a leading role on the village council also held important positions in the religious societies" (Trigger, 1969:73).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Because religion was synonymous with all aspects of Huron life, there is no sense of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 30000

Notes: "The population that is usually quoted for the Huron prior to the epidemics that began to decimate them in 1636 is 30,000. This figure has been accepted as highly reliable because it is found in the writings of Champlain, Sagard, and the Jesuits" (Trigger, 1969:12).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The Huron had numerous formal structures that cut across clan and village lines. One such kind of institution was the curing societies, each of which performed specific rituals that were believed to cure certain kinds of disease...Each of the curing societies had a leader, whose office appears to have been hereditary. Very often, these leaders seem to have been important chiefs whose ritual office complemented and strengthened their secular authority" (Trigger, 1969:97-98).

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "The Huron recognized four kinds of shamans: those who were able to control the wind and rain, those who could predict future events, those who could find lost objects, and, finally, those who could heal the sick. Of these, the last were the most important. Only men appear to have served as curers; women who claimed supernatural powers restricted themselves to various forms of divination" (Trigger, 1969:115).

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: "The Jesuits report that in former times a man who wished to become an arendiwane [shaman] fasted in seclusion for an entire month. During this time he saw no one except an assistant who brought him provisions and who likewise fasted. Even at the time the reports were written prolonged fasting and the avoidance of sexual contact were necessary to become a medicine man" (Trigger, 1969:115-116).

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: "Medicine men obtained their powers through visions or dreams in which their familiar spirit revealed itself to them" (Trigger, 1969:115).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: "Specialized knowledge of Huron beliefs and traditions was the property of certain old men, who at feasts were called upon to recite their stories. In this way, the traditions of the past were made known to the younger generation and the solidarity of Huron society, past and present, was reaffirmed" (Trigger, 1976:75).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: "...[the Huron] did not construct special buildings, shrines, or alters for religious purposes" (Trigger, 1969:91).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: "...[the Huron] did not construct special buildings, shrines, or alters for religious purposes" (Trigger, 1969:91).

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "The Huron believed in the immortality of the soul which they thought to be corporeal; this soul was a body as large as that which it animated and was divisible" (Tooker, 1964:140). "When the corpse was taken to the cemetery, its soul was believed to walk ahead of it and to remain near the body until the Feast of the Dead...Most Huron believed that they had two souls. One remained with the body after the Feast of the Dead and did not leave it unless it was reborn as a child...The other soul left the body

at the Feast of the Dead and traveled to a village of the dead located in the west" (Trigger, 1969:103).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: "Human beings, as well as animals and what we would regard as inanimate objects, were believed to have souls. These souls were as large as the body they animated and had the same shape. Human souls had several parts, each corresponding to some aspect of behavior such as being active, having knowledge, exercising judgement, or desiring things. Each of these aspects of the soul had its own name" (Trigger, 1969:103).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Most Huron believed that they had two souls. One remained with the body after the Feast of the Dead and did not leave it unless it was reborn as a child...The other soul left the body at the Feast of the Dead and traveled to a village of the dead located in the west" (Trigger, 1969:103).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Most Huron believed that they had two souls. One remained with the body after the Feast of the Dead and did not leave it unless it was reborn as a child...The other soul left the body at the Feast of the Dead and traveled to a village of the dead located in the west. Each Huron tribe or major village was believed to have its counterpart in the land of the dead. There also lived Aataentsic and Iouskeha." (Trigger, 1969:103).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: The afterlife is described by the Huron as being in a westward direction.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "The Huron believed that souls entered other bodies after death. After the Feast of the Dead, one of the two souls of the deceased person remained in the pit and did not leave it unless a woman bore it again as a child. A proof of this rebirth was the resemblance of some living persons to dead ones" (Tooker, 1964:140).

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: Tooker, 1964:140

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "...the most distinctive Huron customs were those associated with the burial of the dead. In this, they were heirs of a longstanding tradition among the peoples of the Northeast" (Trigger, 1969:102).

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: "The bodies of those who died violent deaths were immediately buried or burned, and they were not dug up and reburied at the Feast of the Dead" (Trigger, 1969:104).

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "At the cemetery has been constructed a tomb 8 to 10 feet high made of bark, supported on four posts, and somewhat painted...not all bodies were put into the tomb raised on four posts. A few bodies were buried in the ground, and over them a hut or shrine of bark was built" (Tooker, 1964:130-131). For a detailed description of burial practices, see Tooker, 1964:130-133.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: "As soon as a man died, his body was flexed in a crouching position, wrapped tightly in his finest robe, and laid on the mat on which he had died" (Trigger, 1969:105).

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: "The bodies of those who had not died violent deaths did not remain in the village cemeteries, but were removed from their coffins and reburied in a common bone pit at the Feast of the Dead, an observance that the Huron generally referred to as "the kettle." This ceremony was held at about ten- or twelve-year intervals" (Trigger, 1969:106-107).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "Only an occasional wampum collar, a comb, a gourd full of oil, or a few loaves of bread were placed in the coffin with the deceased" (Trigger, 1969:106).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "Burial usually took place on the third day after death...The funeral began at daybreak with a meal. This was provided to feed the guests who had arrived from elsewhere, to nourish the soul of the dead man and as a further expression of grief and consolation of the community...The body was then covered with a beaver robe and four men carried it on a mat to the cemetery, the whole village following in silence. There a tomb had been prepared. At least among the Attignawantan, most of these tombs consisted of a bark coffin supported on four posts 8-10 feet high and sparsely painted. In some villages a few corpses were buried in the ground, a bark hut or shrine was built over the grave, and a stake fence was erected to keep out dogs and wild animals" (Trigger, 1969:105-106).

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: (Trigger, 1969:105-106)

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Secondary burial in common bone pit

Notes: "The bodies of those who had not died violent deaths did not remain in the village cemeteries, but were removed from their coffins and reburied in a common bone pit at the Feast of the Dead, an observance that the Huron generally referred to as "the kettle." This ceremony was held at about ten- or twelve-year intervals" (Trigger, 1969:106-107).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: A variety of supernatural beings are present among the Huron. See questions below for more information.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, Religion: High Gods [note, identical to Ethnographic Atlas variable 34], a high god is present but otiose or not concerned with human affairs (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). "Although the Huron had no well-organized pantheon of deities, their most important spirit was the sky, who controlled the weather and assisted human beings in times of need" (Trigger, 1976:76).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "Although the Huron had no well-organized pantheon of deities, their most important spirit was the sky, who controlled the weather and assisted human beings in times of need" (Trigger, 1976:76).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: There is no monarch among the Huron.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: There is no monarch among the Huron.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, Religion: High Gods [note, identical to Ethnographic Atlas variable 34], a high god is present but otiose or not concerned with human affairs (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

– Yes

Notes: "The most important of all spirits was the sky. It controlled the seasons, held in check the winds and waves, and assisted men in times of need. The sky was invoked whenever an important bargain or treaty was concluded and it was believed that if such an oath were broken, the sky would punish the offender. Offerings of tobacco were made to the sky, and it was thought highly improper to mock it" (Trigger, 1969:91).

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– I don't know

Notes: The sky is described as helping humans in time of need. However, it is unclear if this is a reward. (See Trigger, 1969:91).

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Trigger, 1969:91

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Although the Huron had no well-organized pantheon of deities, their most important spirit was the sky, who controlled the weather and assisted human beings in times of need" (Trigger, 1976:76).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– I don't know

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, Religion: High Gods [note, identical to Ethnographic Atlas variable 34], a high god is present but otiose or not concerned with human affairs (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Because the high god is otiose, it is presumed that the high god does not actively communicate with the living. However, Trigger (1969:91) describes the high god as having deliberate causal efficacy in the world of the living. It is unclear if the high god communicates with the living.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Previously human spirits are present, but not described in substantial ethnographic detail. See questions below for available information.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "In the villages of the dead, life was much the same as it had been on earth. The souls tilled the soil, went hunting and fishing, and participated in feasts and dances. The souls of food or utensils that the living buried with the dead were used by them in the afterlife. In spite of these similarities to the land of the living, the souls of the dead were not happy and are said to have complained day and night" (Trigger, 1969:104).

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: "The souls in the afterlife needed to drink, eat, clothe themselves, and till the ground as they did while they were alive" (Tooker, 1964:141-142).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "The Huron claimed knowledge of the hereafter from souls who had visited them in dreams or from the visits that the souls of the living had made to the land of the dead" (Trigger, 1969:104).

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: "The Huron claimed knowledge of the hereafter from souls who had visited them in dreams or from the visits that the souls of the living had made to the land of the dead" (Trigger, 1969:104).

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Notes: "The Huron claimed knowledge of the hereafter from souls who had visited them in dreams or from the visits that the souls of the living had made to the land of the dead" (Trigger, 1969:104).

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: The Huron do not have a monarch.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The most extensive data that have been preserved concern two of the most important

and best-personified Huron supernatural beings: louskeha and Aataentsic" (Trigger, 1969:91). "The Huron believed that animate spirits resided in the earth, the rivers, lakes, certain rocks, and the sky and had control over journeying, trading, war feasts, disease, and other matters" (Tooker, 1964:80).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "louskeha sometimes visited the Huron country. If he appeared in the cornfields carrying a well-developed stalk of corn, it signified a good harvest; if he was seen gnawing on a human leg, the crops would be bad. louskeha and Aataentsic also attended festivals in Huronia disguised as mortals" (Trigger, 1969:92).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "...[tobacco] was thrown into the water of a great lake in order to calm it and to appease a spirit (Iannaoa) who, in despair, once cast himself into a lake and who caused these storms" (Tooker, 1964:81).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "louskeha was portrayed as having made the world habitable and as having filled it with plants and animals that were useful to mankind. He made the crops grow and protected human beings from all kinds of malevolent influences. While he was capable of violence...it is clear that louskeha was primarily associated with benevolent, creative endeavors" (Trigger, 1969:93).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "Far from helping to sustain life, Aataentsic sought to spoil the good that louskeha had accomplished. She afflicted mankind with sickness and death and sought to hurt human beings whenever she could" (Trigger, 1969:93).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mixed human-divine beings.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Various types of supernatural beings are present, including a high god, previously human spirits, as well as non-human supernatural beings. See questions above for more details on these supernatural beings.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "The most important of all spirits was the sky. It controlled the seasons, held in check the winds and waves, and assisted men in times of need. The sky was invoked whenever an important bargain or treaty was concluded and it was believed that if such an oath were broken, the sky would punish the offender. Offerings of tobacco were made to the sky, and it was thought highly improper to mock it" (Trigger, 1969:91).

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: "The most important of all spirits was the sky. It controlled the seasons, held in check the winds and waves, and assisted men in times of need. The sky was invoked whenever an important bargain or treaty was concluded and it was believed that if such an oath were broken, the sky would punish the offender. Offerings of tobacco were made to the sky, and it was thought highly improper to mock it" (Trigger, 1969:91).

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: "The [corpse preparation/burial] ceremony [for a person who died by drowning or by freezing] was performed to appease the Sky or the Lake who was believed to be angry. If it was not performed, disastrous changes of weather and accompanying accidents would follow as a result of its anger" (Tooker, 1964:132).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "The most important of all spirits was the sky. It controlled the seasons, held in check the winds and waves, and assisted men in times of need. The sky was invoked whenever an important bargain or treaty was concluded and it was believed that if such an oath were broken, the sky would punish the offender. Offerings of tobacco were made to the sky, and it was thought highly improper to mock it" (Trigger, 1969:91).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: The only ethnographic descriptions of direct supernatural punishment describe the high god as the agent of punishment (see Trigger, 1969:91; Trigger, 1976:76).

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The only ethnographic descriptions of direct supernatural punishment describe the high god as the agent of punishment (see Trigger, 1969:91; Trigger, 1976:76).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information regarding the reasons for supernatural punishment.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: "The [corpse preparation/burial] ceremony [for a person who died by drowning or by freezing] was performed to appease the Sky or the Lake who was believed to be angry. If it was not performed, disastrous changes of weather and accompanying accidents would follow as a result of its anger" (Tooker, 1964:132).

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "The most important of all spirits was the sky. It controlled the seasons, held in check the winds and waves, and assisted men in times of need. The sky was invoked whenever an important bargain or treaty was concluded and it was believed that if such an oath were broken, the sky would punish the offender. Offerings of tobacco were made to the sky, and it was thought highly improper to mock it" (Trigger, 1969:91).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: "The [corpse preparation/burial] ceremony [for a person who died by drowning or by freezing] was performed to appease the Sky or the Lake who was believed to be angry. If it was not performed, disastrous changes of weather and accompanying accidents would follow as a result of its anger" (Tooker, 1964:132).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: "...sexual abstinence was important for the accomplishment of many activities of a sacred character; however, not even the most powerful shamans ever practised sexual continence for life, or even for long periods, and the Huron had no equivalent of the European concept of religious celibacy" (Trigger, 1976:79).

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: For a more detailed account of prisoner sacrifice see Trigger, 1976:73-75.

↳ Commoners:

– No

↳ Elites:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Prisoners

Notes: "...in addition to being an act of blood revenge, the prisoner's death was viewed as a sacrifice to the sun" (Trigger, 1976:73).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: While participation in small-scale rituals is not explicitly required, "observances of a religious nature were associated with every type of Huron activity" (Trigger, 1976:76).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "According to the Jesuits, the Huron had four types of feasts. The largest and most magnificent were the atouronta ochien, or singing feasts. Often, hundreds of guests from all over Huronia attended these feasts...feasts of this type appear to have been part of the annual celebrations that accompanied the meeting of the confederacy council. The second type was the enditeuhwa or thanksgiving feast. The purpose of this type of feast is not entirely clear. These feasts were less elaborate than the singing feasts and appear to have been given by individuals to rejoice for special fortune...the final two categories of feasts were curing feasts and the athataion, or farewell feasts. The latter were given by a man on the point of death. Both of these were concerned with a crisis in the life of an individual" (Trigger, 1969:94).

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Notes: "Like the other people of the Northeast, the Huron lacked specialists who performed regular religious ceremonies on behalf of the whole community, and they did not construct special buildings, shrines, or alters for religious purposes" (Trigger, 1969:91).

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Notes: "Like the other people of the Northeast, the Huron lacked specialists who performed regular religious ceremonies on behalf of the whole community, and they did not construct special buildings, shrines, or alters for religious purposes" (Trigger, 1969:91).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: The Huron have one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a chiefdom (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock

and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that among the Huron, routes of land transport included unimproved trails (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Based off this information, it can be assumed that transportation infrastructure is not present.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that among the Huron, routes of land transport included unimproved trails (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Based off this information, it can be assumed that transportation infrastructure is not present.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "The French were at first puzzled, then intrigued, to see a government maintaining law and order among many thousands of people without the aid of a police force, imprisonment, or capital punishment..." (Trigger, 1969:71).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: "The French were at first puzzled, then intrigued, to see a government maintaining law and order among many thousands of people without the aid of a police force, imprisonment, or capital punishment..." (Trigger, 1969:71).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Huron rely primarily on agriculture (extensive/shifting) for subsistence, with fishing as a secondary form of subsistence technology. Hunting and gathering supplement the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Huron rely primarily on agriculture (extensive/shifting) for subsistence, with fishing as a secondary form of subsistence technology. Hunting and gathering supplement the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.